

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Oxalic Acid, Induced by Potassium Persulphate

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Activation of oxalic acid by oxidising agents, such as KMnO_4 , $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, etc., exhibited in the ready reduction of mercuric chloride to mercurous state, was first observed by Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 690; this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 203). The present authors studied the kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid, induced by potassium persulphate (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 405), and derived an expression for the rate process on the mechanism suggested. The present note deals with the dependence of period of induction on the concentration of the reactants and the relationship among the amounts of inductor ($\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$), actor ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$), and acceptor (HgCl_2) on the total amount of calomel formed.

Procedure.—The flasks containing the reaction mixture were kept in a thermostat maintained at 60° . After 60 minutes the precipitated mercurous chloride was filtered through a double-walled funnel at ice-water temperature to arrest the reaction. It was then estimated volumetrically by titrating against $0.1N\text{-KIO}_3$ solution (*loc. cit.*). The time between mixing of the reactants and the first appearance of Hg_2Cl_2 precipitate was noted as the period of induction.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the dependence of induction period and the amount of calomel formed (or mercuric chloride reduced) in one hour, respectively, on the concentrations of the reactants at 60° .

Conc. (mol.).

FIG. 1

1. Oxalic acid.
2. HgCl_2 .
3. $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$.

Conc. (moles).

FIG. 2

For curves 1 (both figs.), the initial concentrations of the persulphate and mercuric chloride were kept $0.02M$ each, whereas that of oxalic acid was varied. Similarly for curves

2 and 3, the concentrations of mercuric chloride and persulphate, respectively, were varied while those of the other two reactants were at 0.02 *M* each.

Fig. 1 shows that increase of concentration of any of the reactants decreases the period of induction. Fig. 2, curve 1 shows that the reduction of mercuric chloride increases by increasing the concentration of oxalic acid. It is found to be proportional to the acid concentration up to 0.04*M* and then slows down. The reduction is proportional to the concentration of mercuric chloride (curve 2). The reduction increases by increasing the concentration of persulphate to 0.02*M* only and then suffers inhibition.

Neither $C_2O_4^{2-}$ nor $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion alone is able to reduce mercuric chloride, but a mixture of the two does so. This clearly suggests that as a result of interaction of the two ions some active product is produced which reduces Hg^{2+} ion to Hg_2^{2+} state. This active product is possibly the CO_2^- radical, which may be formed during the oxidation of oxalic acid by the persulphate, as has been observed in the oxidation of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate (Weiss, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 53, 188) and halogens (Griffith and McKeown, *ibid.*, 1932, 28, 752.)

The role of CO_2^- and SO_4^- radicals as intermediates in the reduction of mercuric chloride has been shown in the mechanism suggested by the authors (*loc. cit.*) and the rate expression derived therefrom explains fully the curves in Fig. 2. The time required for thermal activation of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion to break into SO_4^- radical is the induction period and this decreases on increasing the concentration of any of the reactants.